

JURISPRUDENCE

UN AND OTHER ORGANIZATIONS ON WAY OF CONTEMPORARY UKRAINIAN ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION

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Abstract

Article proposed are devoted to the problem of international response to environmental and economic challenges of Russian aggression against Ukraine. The problem of the activities of UN, IAEA, UNICEF and UNESCO in this context in accordance with their role in solving the global problems of mankind is presented. In general maintained that the UN directly and through its programs (particularly, UNDP) plays a leading environmental role in relation to Ukraine among international organizations during the war. This role is due to both programs of stable development and conservation of the environment, as well as investments in the environmental sector and the promotion of an ecological-friendly economy. The author's summarizing in the studied area are given.

Keywords: environmental protection, UN, IAEA, UNICEF, UNESCO, problems of mankind, wartime Ukraine.

Introduction. Resolution of the mankind's global problems in its totality is inextricably linked to the field of environmental protection, since climate change associated with the anthropogenic factor poses a direct threat to the physical existence of human civilization. In respect to these circumstances, the leading role is given to international organizations dedicated to ensuring and guaranteeing the world law and order within the framework of existing international treaties, conventions and agreements. At the same time, their priority should be paid to the regions in which the theater of operations unfolds, which, today, is the geographical center of Europe represented by Ukraine. Aforesaid is due to the relevance of the study proposed.

Since the research topic represents current events, the scientific community has not yet had time to properly pay attention to it, at least, in papers despite that hundreds of international experts from all over the world are involved in solving the environmental problems of wartime Ukraine [10].

Hence, the problem of the environmental damage and international organizations' impact on its reduce and relief consequences, is gaining prominence among the current problems of public, domestic and international law in contemporary epoch.

The purpose of these papers is to evaluate the level of international environmental legal protection and respond on contemporary threats in the context of war economic activities in Ukraine.

Materials and Methods. Presented papers has done with assistance of formal and compares methods as special and ontology, deduction, analysis ad synthesis as common, which led to obtain a new data and background for discussion and further investigations from contemporary scientific viewpoint. Thereof, research methodology is based on general scientific methods such as analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, analogy and empirical methods - observation, comparison and so on and so forth.

Methodological basis of the survey, presumably, is a dialectical method, the introduction of which provides an opportunity to study the object and subject of research in their gnoseological unity, as well as the nature of medical law development and their impact, as cause and effect.

Results and Discussion. In September 2015, at the 70th session of the UN General Assembly, the UN Summit on Sustainable Development was held. The summit's summary document, "Transforming Our World: Agenda for Sustainable Development 2030," identified 17 sustainable development goals and a number of supporting goals. Like other UN member states, Ukraine has joined the global process of sustainable development. The Sustainable Development Goals are the global call to action to end poverty, protect the earth's environment and climate, and ensure that people everywhere can enjoy peace and prosperity. These are the goals the UN is working on in Ukraine [2].

Minister of Environmental Protection and Natural Resources of Ukraine Ruslan Strilets met with UN Environment Programme Executive Director Inger Andersen on the sidelines of the Africa Climate Summit. The parties discussed the final stages of the assessment of the consequences of the Kakhovka hydroelectric power plant blow-up and the roadmap for the restoration of southern Ukraine [5].

According to the Ministry of Environmental Protection and Natural Resources, around 30 percent of the country's protected areas, covering more than 1.2 million hectares, have been bombed, polluted, burned, or otherwise affected by military maneuvers. Massive forest fires spread as the fighting rages on, while attacks on fuel and industrial facilities have caused chemicals to leach into rivers and groundwater. UNDP interim Representative Jaco Cilliers said the environmental consequences of the war are widespread and devastating. "The use of explosive ordnance in urban areas, for example, is creating vast quantities of debris and rubble, which can cause air, water, and soil pollution," he said. "Damage to light industry and environmentally

sensitive infrastructure such as water treatment plants and water sanitation utilities is also creating problems that can take years to remediate. This new Centre will both monitor and explore ways to remediate the impacts.” Tobias Thyberg, Ambassador Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary of Sweden to Ukraine, said it is of critical importance to monitor and document the war’s environmental impacts. “These impacts can harm the health and well-being of both humans and wildlife, disrupt ecosystems, and contribute to climate change,” he said. “While large resources and funding now need to go toward Ukraine’s efforts to defend itself against Russia’s aggression, it remains important to also continue funding environmental protection and conservation efforts, to ensure that Ukraine can continue protecting its environment while defending itself against Russia’s illegal war. We hope the Centre will help raise awareness of these factors, inform the recovery process with facts on the ground, and help to conserve Ukraine’s natural heritage for future generations” [4].

UNECE welcomes the approval by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of the procedure for maintaining a national Register of emissions and pollutants. This Register, which will be operational from 8 October 2023, is expected to facilitate the free provision to the public of information on pollution, such as greenhouse gas emissions, and to facilitate the objective reporting of enterprises on their environmental emissions [7].

Amid the ongoing aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine, adoption by the UN General Assembly of resolutions 68/262 «Territorial integrity of Ukraine» (27.03.2014), 71/205, 72/190, 73/263, 74/168 and 75/192 «Situation of human rights in the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol, Ukraine» (19.12.2016, 19.12.2017, 22.12.2018, 18.12.2019), as well as 73/194, 74/17 and 75/29 «Problem of militarization of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol, Ukraine, as well as parts of the Black Sea and the Sea of Azov» (17.12.2018, 9.12.2019 and 7.12.2020) is instrumental in political and legal terms. In the framework of cooperation with the United Nations system, Ukraine received assistance in the amount of more than \$200 million. The United States is implementing more than 300 projects in the field of human rights protection, social assistance, civil society development, environmental protection and nuclear energy. In 2019, the United Nations portfolio of such assistance included 12 projects with an estimated cost of \$46 million. In response to the devastating humanitarian consequences of Russian aggression against Ukraine and the activities of illegal armed groups in the east of our country, cooperation between Ukraine and the United Nations in the humanitarian field has increased exponentially. Humanitarian assistance is provided by UN bodies responsible for operational activities (UNHCR, OCHA, UNDP, WHO, UNFPA, UNICEF and other relevant bodies) [1].

Just over a year after the IAEA established a permanent presence at Europe’s largest nuclear power plant (NPP) to help prevent an accident there during the conflict in Ukraine, the overall situation at the facility remains highly precarious. At the plant, the IAEA ex-

perts observed the continued presence of mines between the perimeter fences, but they did not see any additional ones during their walkdown activities across the site. However, they have still not been granted access to the rooftops of reactor units 1, 2, 5 and 6. The IAEA team has also been requesting a walkdown of all six turbine halls, one after the other, to be able to fully assess, at one time, whether there may be any items present that may be in contravention of the five principles. At present, this request has not been granted. Three months after the downstream Kakhovka dam was destroyed – causing the depletion of the huge reservoir that the ZNPP had been relying on to cool its reactors and spent fuel – the plant continues work on expanding access to other sources of water, for example through the drilling of groundwater wells. So far, seven such wells of a planned total of 10-12 have been completed. In recent days, the IAEA team observed – on two separate occasions – the operation of these wells supplying the sprinkler ponds, which are located next to the six reactors and used for the plant’s cooling functions. The ZNPP has informed the IAEA team that the seven wells currently operating are accounting for just over half of the approximately 250 cubic meters of water per hour that are required to maintain the cooling water in the sprinkler ponds. This assumes all units remain in a shutdown state. The remaining volume of cooling water is currently pumped from the site’s drainage system. As a result of the new wells, the ZNPP also informed the IAEA that the height of the groundwater had only declined by a very minor level. The IAEA team reported that the ZNPP is performing maintenance on different components and safety systems at the facility, whose six reactors remain shut down, one in hot shutdown and the others in cold shutdown. Maintenance activities of the safety systems of unit 4 are also taking place, including of its transformer, heat exchangers and emergency diesel generators. Once they are completed, the site will conduct the final test of the steam generator that was repaired after a water leak was detected in this unit last month. Nowadays, the IAEA team also conducted other walkdown activities within the site perimeter, including at the main control room, emergency control room and the safety systems rooms of unit 6 and the turbine hall of unit 3 where the team reported that there was no military equipment present at the time of its visit. This morning the IAEA experts visited the turbine hall of reactor unit 1 where they observed a total of fifteen vehicles, but no heavy weapons. The ZNPP continues to receive off-site power from the last remaining 750 kilovolt (kV) power line and a single 330kV backup power line. The IAEA experts were informed by the ZNPP that the site currently does not have any information on the status of repairs of the damaged off-site power lines as they all pass through the military conflict areas. Elsewhere in Ukraine, rotations of the IAEA experts have been conducted this week at the Khmelnytsky, Rivne and South Ukraine NPPs and a rotation of the team at the Chornobyl site is scheduled for next week. The IAEA teams at the four sites did not report any nuclear safety or security issues [8].

UNICEF is working to ensure sustainable management of water resources and solid waste in Ukraine's conflict-affected areas by improving fair access to safe drinking water and safe sanitation, reducing exposure to environmental risks, improving hygiene in communities, schools and health facilities and engaging young people for environmental-friendly activities [9].

Additionally, as the war in Ukraine continues, humanitarian conditions for children in Ukraine keep deteriorating. Around two-thirds of children are now displaced either within Ukraine or in neighboring countries. Children continue to be killed, injured and deeply traumatized by the devastating violence around them. They are terrified, in shock, and desperate for safety, stability, protection and psychosocial care. Attacks using explosive weapons in populated urban areas continue to inflict civilian casualties and considerable damage to essential infrastructure and services. Children are being forced to protect themselves in underground shelters and subway stations, where conditions are dire [6].

UNESCO's response focuses on all key areas of heritage: advising professionals on how to protect buildings and safeguard living heritage, delivering protective equipment, digitizing works of art and archives, advising the national authorities in updating policies and strategies, delivering protective equipment and materials, digitizing works of art and archives, supporting inventory-making, supporting artists and cultural professionals, integrating living heritage in education, and coordinating the fight against the illicit trafficking of cultural property, and assessing damage. The priority: preventing destruction and looting. From the start of the war, UNESCO experts provided advice to Ukrainian cultural professionals on how to secure buildings, improve fire-fighting systems and identify safe shelters for works of art that could be moved. The Organization has also delivered protective material for the facades of cultural buildings and for outdoor works of art such as statues, as well as electric generators. UNESCO supports the authorities in marking cultural sites with the Blue Shield emblem of the 1954 Convention, which indicates that these properties are under the protection of international law and that targeting them can lead to prosecution. The Organization also provided urgent repair works for cultural sites, for example in Kharkiv, Kyiv and Odesa. From the beginning of the war, UNESCO undertook a preliminary assessment of the damage inflicted on Ukrainian cultural property. This analysis is conducted by collecting, cross-checking and studying information on damage from several reliable sources. To further improve this method, UNESCO decided in May 2022 to systematically use satellite images, with the expertise of UNITAR/UNOSAT. These images allow verifying the exact state of cultural sites, especially when they are currently inaccessible by land, notably when they are located on the front line. UNESCO created a dedicated online platform to list and georeference all these assessments. These efforts are being supplemented by in situ damage assessments [3].

Conclusions. 1. The UN directly and through its programs (particularly, UNDP) plays a leading envi-

ronmental role in relation to Ukraine among international organizations during the war. This role is due to both programs of stable development and conservation of the environment, as well as investments in the environmental sector and the promotion of an ecological-friendly economy.

2. The role of the IAEA comes down to monitoring the physical and technical stability of nuclear power plants, ensuring their nuclear safety, which avoids the largest man-made catastrophe in human history and ensures its survival on the Earth. At the same time, the IAEA is concerned about the proper functioning of water supply facilities that can serve as cooling agents for nuclear power plants.

3. UNICEF is working to ensure sustainable management of water resources and solid waste in Ukraine's conflict-affected areas by improving fair access to safe drinking water and safe sanitation, reducing exposure to environmental risks, improving hygiene in communities, schools and health facilities and engaging young people for environmental-friendly activities.

4. UNESCO's response focuses on all key areas of heritage: advising professionals on how to protect buildings and safeguard living heritage, delivering protective equipment, digitizing works of art and archives, advising the national authorities in updating policies and strategies, delivering protective equipment and materials, digitizing works of art and archives, supporting inventory-making, supporting artists and cultural professionals, integrating living heritage in education, and coordinating the fight against the illicit trafficking of cultural property, and assessing damage. The priority: preventing destruction and looting.

5. Aforesaid and other tasks are resolved by international organizations not only through monitoring and observation, but also through the adoption of acts of international law, in particular, resolutions and memoranda, appeals to heads of state and governments of other countries and their associations, which makes it allowable to draw the attention of the advanced international community to the problems of the ecological and economic survival of Ukraine in the context of aggressive military operations.

At the same time, the problem of subsequent nuclear disarmament, the liberation of protected facilities and reserves in order to preserve biodiversity on our planet remains unresolved, which requires further scientific research and investigations.

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